

Science

ON GENERALIGATIONS OF PARTITION FUNCTIONS

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ABSTRACT

In 1742, Leonhard Euler invented the generating function for $P(n)$. Godfrey Harold Hardy said Srinivasa Ramanujan was the first, and up to now the only, Mathematician to discover any such properties of $P(n)$. In 1916, Ramanujan defined the generating functions for $X(n), Y(n)$. In 2014, Sabuj developed the generating functions for $\cdot$. In 2005, George E. Andrews found the generating functions for $\cdot$. In 1916, Ramanujan showed the generating functions for $\cdot, \cdot$, and $\cdot$. This article shows how to prove the Theorems with the help of various auxiliary functions collected from Ramanujan's Lost Notebook. In 1967, George E. Andrews defined the generating functions for $P1r(n)$ and $P2r(n)$. In this article these generating functions are discussed elaborately. This article shows how to prove the theorem $P2r(n) = P3r(n)$ with a numerical example when $n = 9$ and $r = 2$. In 1995, Fokkink, Fokkink and Wang defined the $\cdot$ in terms of $\cdot$, where $\cdot$ is the smallest part of partition. In 2013, Andrews, Garvan and Liang extended the FFW-function and defined the generating function for FFW (z, n) in differnt way.

Keywords:

FFW-function; Operator; Rogers- Ramanujan Identities; Ramanujan's Lost Notebook.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In this article, we give some related definitions of $P(n)$, $P^o(n), P^d(n)$, $X(n), Y(n)$, $X^1(n), Y^1(n)$ and $P_e^d(n)$, $C'(n), C''(n)$, $C_1'(n), C_1''(n)$, $P'(n), P''(n), P_1^r(n), P_2^r(n), P_3^r(n)$, $FFW(n)$, $d(n)$, $(x)_\infty, (x^2; x)_\infty, (zx)_\infty, (x)_k$ and $(x^{k+1}; x)_\infty$. In section 1.3, we generate the generating function for $P(n)$. In section 1.4, we give the generating functions for $P^o(n), P^d(n)$, and prove the Corollary 1.1 by mathematical expression, and prove the Theorem 1.1 with an example. In section 1.5, we generate the generating functions for $X(n), Y(n)$ and prove the Corollary 1.2 by mathematical expression and prove the Remark 1.1 with an example. In section 1.6 we develop the generating functions for $X^1(n), Y^1(n)$ and $P_e^d(n)$ and prove the Corollary 1.3 in terms of $X^1(n), Y^1(n)$ and

prove the another Corollary 1.4 in terms of $P_e^d(n)$ and $X^1(n)$. In section 1.7, we discuss the generating functions for $C'(n), C''(n)$, and quite some special functions collected from Ramanujan's lost notebook and unpublished papers, and prove the Theorem 1.2 with an example. In section 1.8, we give the generating functions for $C_1'(n), C_1''(n)$, and prove the Theorem 1.3 with example. In section 1.9, we give the generating functions for $P'(n), P''(n)$ and prove the Corollary 1.5 in terms of $P'(n), P''(n)$ and prove the Theorem 1.4 with an example. In section 1.10, we generate the generating functions for $P_1^2(n), P_2^2(n), P_2^r(n), P_3^r(n)$ and prove the Corollary 1.6 in terms of $P_1^r(n), P_2^r(n)$, and prove the Theorem 1.5 with an example. Finally in section 1.11, we discuss the generating function for FFW (n) and give the Relation 1.1 in terms of $FFW(n), d(n)$, and prove the Corollaries 1.7, 1.8, 1.9 and 1.10 with the help of their generating functions.

1.2. SOME RELATED DEFINITIONS

$P(n)$: The number of partitions of n. Example: 4, 3+1, 2+2, 2+1+1, 1+1+1+1 $\therefore P(4)=5$.

$P^o(n)$: The number of partitions of n into odd parts.

$P^d(n)$: The number of partitions of n into distinct parts.

$X(n)$: The number of partitions of n with no part repeated more than twice.

$Y(n)$: The number of partitions of n with no part divisible by 3.

$X^1(n)$: The number of partitions of n with no part repeated more than thrice .

$Y^1(n)$: The number of partitions of n with no part divisible by 4.

$P_e^d(n)$: The number of partitions of n into even distinct parts.

$C'(n)$: The number of partitions of n into parts of the forms $5m + 1$ and $5m + 4$.

$C''(n)$: The number of partitions of n into parts of the forms $5m + 2$ and $5m + 3$.

$C_1'(n)$: The number of partitions of n into parts without repetitions or parts whose minimal difference is 2.

$C_1''(n)$: The number of partitions of n into parts not less than 2 and with minimal difference 2.

$P'(n)$: The number of partitions of n into parts of the form $n = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_r$,

where $a_i - a_{i+1} \geq 3$ and if $3|a_i$, then $a_i - a_{i+1} > 3$

$P''(n)$: The number of partitions of n into parts congruent to $\pm 1 \pmod{6}$.

$P_1^r(n)$: The number of partitions of n into part that are either even or not congruent to $4r - 2 \pmod{4r}$ or odd and congruent to $2r - 1, 4r - 1 \pmod{4r}$.

$P_2^r(n)$: The number of partitions of n into parts that are either even or else congruent to $2r - 1 \pmod{2r}$ with the further restriction that only even parts may be repeated.

$P_3^r(n)$: The number of partitions of n of the form $n = b_1 + b_2 + \dots + b_s$, where $b_i \geq b_{i+1}$, and for b_i odd, $b_i - b_{i+1} \geq 2r - 1$ ($1 \leq i \leq s$, where $b_{s+1} = 0$).

FFW (n): Let D denote the set of partitions into distinct parts. We define;

$$FFW(n) = \sum_{\substack{\pi \in D \\ |\pi|=n}} (-1)^{\#(\pi)-1} s(\pi),$$

where $s(\pi)$ is the smallest part of a partition π , and $\#(\pi)$ is the number of parts .

$d(n)$: The number of positive divisors of n like $d(1)=1, d(2)=2, d(3)=2, \dots$

Product Notations:

$$(x; x)_{\infty} = (x)_{\infty} = (1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots$$

$$(x^2; x)_{\infty} = (1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots$$

$$(zx)_{\infty} = (1-zx)(1-zx^2)\dots \quad \text{where } |x| < 1.$$

$$(x)_k = (1-x)(1-x^2)\dots(1-x^k)$$

$$(x^{k+1}; x)_{\infty} = (1-x^{k+1})(1-x^{k+2})\dots$$

1.3. PARTITION

A partition of n is a division of n into any number of positive integral parts. Then the sum of the integral parts or summands is n . The order of the parts and arrangement in a division of n are irrelevant and the parts are arranged in descending order. Usually a partition of n is denoted by Greek letters π . We denote the number of partitions of n by $P(n)$. It is convenient to define

$P(0) = 1$ and $P(n) = 0$ for negative integer of n .

Let $A = \{a_1, a_2, \dots, a_r, \dots\}$ be a finite or infinite set of positive integers. If $a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_r = n$, with $a_r \in A$ ($r = 1, 2, 3, \dots$). Here repetitions are allowed. Then we say that the sum $a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_r$ is a partition of n into parts belonging to the set A . So that, $3+2+1$ is a partition of 6. If a partition contains p numbers, it is called a partition of n into p parts or shortly a p -partition of n . Hence, $9 = 4+2+1+1+1$, and we can say that, $4+2+1+1+1$ is a 5-partition of 9. The order of the parts is irrelevant, the parts to be arranged in descending order of magnitude, $a_1 \geq a_2 \geq a_3 \geq \dots a_r \geq 1$.

Now explain how to find all the partitions of 7 as follows:

First take 7; then 6 allowed by 1; then 5 allowed by all the partitions of 2 (i.e., 2, 1+1); then 4 allowed by all the partitions of 3 (i.e., 3, 2+1, 1+1+1); then 3 allowed by all the partitions of 4, which contain no part greater than 3 (i.e., 3+1, 2+1+1, 1+1+1+1, 2+2); then 2 allowed by all the partitions of 5, which contain no part greater than 2 (i.e., 2+2+1, 2+1+1+1, 1+1+1+1+1); lastly 1+1+1+1+1+1+1. Hence the complete set is;

7, 6+1, 5+2, 5+1+1, 4+3, 4+2+1, 4+1+1+1, 3+3+1, 3+2+1+1, 3+1+1+1+1, 3+2+2, 2+2+2+1, 2+2+1+1+1, 2+1+1+1+1+1, 1+1+1+1+1+1+1.

1.3.1. Generating function for $P(n)$ [Euler (1742)]

$P(n)$ is the number of partitions of n given in Table-1.1

n Type of partitions

$P(n)$

1	1	1
2	2, 1+1	2
3	3, 2+1, 1+1+1	3
4	4, 3+1, 2+2, 2+1+1, 1+1+1+1	5
5	5, 4+1, 3+2, 3+1+1, 2+2+1, 2+1+1+1, 1+1+1+1+1	7
...		...

It is convenient to define $P(0) = 1$, but $P(n) = 0$ for $n < 0$.

We can make an expression as;

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P(0) + P(1)x + P(2)x^2 + P(3)x^3 + P(4)x^4 + P(5)x^5 + \dots \\
 &= 1 + 1.x + 2.x^2 + 3.x^3 + 5.x^4 + 7.x^5 + \dots \\
 &= (1 + x + x^2 + \dots)(1 + x^2 + x^4 + \dots)(1 + x^3 + x^6 + \dots) \dots \\
 &= \frac{1}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3) \dots} \\
 &= \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1-x^i} \\
 \therefore \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^i)} &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P(n)x^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

1.4. Generating Functions for $P^o(n)$ and $P^d(n)$:

[Collected from Ramanujan’s lost notebook]

1.4.1 The generating function for $P^o(n)$;

$P^o(n)$ is the number of partitions of n into odd parts given in Table-1.2

n	Type of partitions	$P^o(n)$
1	1	1
2	1+1	1
3	3, 1+1+1	2
4	3+1, 1+1+1+1	2
5	5, 3+1+1, 1+1+1+1+1	3
...		...

It is convenient to define $P^o(0) = 1$.

We can write an expression for $P^o(n)$ as;

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P^o(0) + P^o(1)x + P^o(2)x^2 + P^o(3)x^3 + P^o(4)x^4 + \dots \\
 &= 1 + 1.x + 1.x^2 + 2.x^3 + 2.x^4 + \dots \\
 &= \frac{1}{(1-x)(1-x^3)(1-x^5) \dots} \quad \text{[Toh, (2011)]} \\
 &= \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{2i-1})}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{2i-1})} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P^o(n)x^n.$$

1.4.2 The generating function for $P^d(n)$;

$P^d(n)$ is the number of partitions of n into distinct parts given in Table-1.3

n	Type of partitions	$P^d(n)$
1	1	1
2	2	1
3	3, 2+1	2
4	4, 3+1	2
5	5, 4+1, 3+2	3
...		...

It is convenient to define $P^d(0)=1$.

We can write an expression for $P^d(n)$ as;

$$\begin{aligned} &P^d(0)+P^d(1)x+P^d(2)x^2+P^d(3)x^3+P^d(4)x^4+\dots \\ &= 1+1.x+1.x^2+2.x^3+2.x^4+\dots \\ &= (1+x)(1+x^2)(1+x^3)\dots \\ &= \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1+x^n) \\ \therefore \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1+x^n) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P^d(n)x^n. \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 1.1: $P^o(n) = P^d(n)$

Proof: From above we get;

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P^o(n)x^n &= \prod_{i=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{2i-1})} \\ &= \frac{1}{(1-x)(1-x^3)(1-x^5)\dots} \\ &= \frac{(1-x^2)(1-x^4)(1-x^6)\dots}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots} \\ &= (1+x)(1+x^2)(1+x^3)\dots \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P^d(n)x^n. \text{ [by above]} \end{aligned}$$

Now equating the coefficient of x^n from both sides we get;

$P^o(n) = P^d(n)$. Hence The Theorem.

Theorem 1.1 [Das (2013)]: The number of partitions of n into odd parts is equal to the number of partitions of n into unequal parts. i.e., $P^o(n) = P^d(n)$.

Proof: We develop an one to one correspondence between the partitions enumerated by $P^o(n)$ and those enumerated by $P^d(n)$. We start with any partition of n into odd parts say $n = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_r$. Among these r odd integers, suppose there are m distinct ones, say $c_1, c_2, \dots, c_m$ by rearranging notation if necessary. Collecting like terms in the partition of n , we get $n = e_1 c_1 + e_2 c_2 + \dots + e_m c_m$. We write each co-efficient e_i as a unique sum of distinct powers of 2, and write each $e_i c_i$ as a sum of terms of the type $2^t c_i$. This gives n as a partition into distinct parts. Thus we have the one to one correspondence. Such as a number k can be expressed uniquely in the binary scale i.e., as $k = 2^a + 2^b + 2^c + \dots (0 \leq a < b < c \dots)$. Hence a partition of n into odd parts can be written as;

$$n = k_1 \cdot 1 + k_2 \cdot 3 + k_3 \cdot 5 + \dots$$

$$= (2^{a_1} + 2^{b_1} + \dots) \cdot 1 + (2^{a_2} + 2^{b_2} + \dots) \cdot 3 + (2^{a_3} + 2^{b_3} + \dots) \cdot 5 + \dots$$

and there is an one to one correspondence between this partitions and the into distinct parts $2^{a_1} \cdot 1, 2^{b_1} \cdot 1, \dots, 2^{a_2} \cdot 3, 2^{b_2} \cdot 3, \dots, 2^{a_3} \cdot 5, 2^{b_3} \cdot 5, \dots$

Conversely let $n = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_r$ be a partition of n into distinct parts. We convert this partition into a partition of n with odd parts. For any even positive integer m can be expressed $2^j f(m)$ as a multiple odd integer. As for example; $4 = 1 \cdot 2^2$, $6 = 3 \cdot 2^1$, $10 = 4 + 6 = 1 \cdot 2^2 + 3 \cdot 2^1$, where 2^j is the highest power of 2 and $f(m)$ is an odd integer. Suppose there are distinct odd integers among $f(a_1), f(a_2), \dots, f(a_r)$. Rearrange the subscripts of necessary so that $f(a_1), f(a_2), \dots, f(a_s)$ are distinct odd integers, and $f(a_{s+1}), f(a_{s+2}), \dots, f(a_r)$ are duplicates of these. Collecting terms, we can write

$$n = \sum_{i=1}^s c_i f(a_i) \text{ with positive integers coefficients } c_i. \text{ The final step is to write each } c_i f(a_i) \text{ in the}$$

form $f(a_1) + f(a_2) + \dots + f(a_i)$ with c_i terms in the sum. Thus n is expressed as a sum of odd integers. Clearly our correspondence is onto so that, $P^o(n) = P^d(n)$.

Numerical Example 1.1:

We take $n = 11$, the list of partitions of 11 into odd parts is given below;

$$11 = 9+1+1 = 7+3+1 = 7+1+1+1+1 = 5+5+1$$

$$= 5+3+1+1+1 = 5+1+1+1+1+1+1 = 5+3+3 = 3+3+3+1+1$$

$$= 3+3+1+1+1+1+1 = 3+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1$$

$$= 1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1.$$

So there are 12 partitions. i.e., $P^o(11) = 12$.

Again the list of partitions of 11 into unequal parts is given below;

$$11 = 10+1 = 9+2 = 8+3 = 8+2+1 = 7+4 = 7+3+1$$

$$= 6+5 = 6+4+1 = 6+3+2 = 5+4+2 = 5+3+2+1.$$

So there are 12 partitions. i.e., $P^d(11) = 12$.

Therefore, $P^o(11) = P^d(11)$.

1.5. Generating functions for $X(n)$ and $Y(n)$:

[Collected from Ramanujan's lost notebook]

1.5.1 The generating function for $X(n)$:

$X(n)$ is the number of partitions of n with no part repeated more than twice given in Table-1.4

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} X(n)x^n &= \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1+x^n+x^{2n}) \\ &= (1+x+x^2)(1+x^2+x^4)(1+x^3+x^6)\dots(1+x^n+x^{2n})\dots\infty \\ &= \frac{1-x^3}{1-x} \cdot \frac{1-x^6}{1-x^2} \cdot \frac{1-x^9}{1-x^3} \dots \frac{1-x^{3n}}{1-x^n} \dots \\ &= \frac{1}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots(1-x^{3n-2})(1-x^{3n-1})\dots} \\ &= \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{3n-2})(1-x^{3n-1})} \\ \therefore \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} X(n)x^n &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} Y(n)x^n. \end{aligned}$$

Equating the coefficient of x^n from both sides we get;

$$X(n) = Y(n). \text{ Hence the Corollary.}$$

Remark 1.1 [Das (2014)]: The number of partitions of n with no part repeated more than twice is equal to the number of partitions of n with no part divisible by 3.

$$\text{i.e., } X(n) = Y(n).$$

Proof: We develop a one-to-one correspondence between the partitions enumerated by $X(n)$ and those enumerated by $Y(n)$. Let $n = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_r$ be a partition of n with no part is repeated more than twice. We transfer this into a partition of n with no part is divisible by 3. If a part a_m of the partition, which is divisible by 3, enumerated by $X(n)$ can be expressed into three equal parts, such that: $6 = 2+2+2$, $3 = 1+1+1$. Rearranging the parts of the partition, we can say that the parts are not divisible by 3. Clearly, our correspondence is one-to-one.

Conversely, we start any partition of n into with no part is divisible by 3, say $n = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_r$, we consider the same part not less than thrice, it would be unique sum by same three parts by taking a group, such that, $5+1+1+1 = 5+3$ and $2+2+2+1+1 = 6+1+1$.

This gives n as a partition with no part is repeated more than twice. Thus, we have the one-to-one correspondence. The corresponding is onto, so that $X(n) = Y(n)$. Hence the Remark.

Numerical Example1.2:

When $n = 8$, the listed partitions of 8 with no part repeated more than twice is given below;
 $8 = 7+1 = 6+2 = 6+1+1 = 5+3 = 5+2+1 = 4+4 = 4+3+1 = 4+2+1+1 = 4+2+2 = 3+3+2 = 3+3+1+1 = 3+2+2+1$.

So, there are 13 partitions i.e., $X(8) = 13$. Again, the list of partitions of 8 with no part is divisible by 3 is given below:

$$8 = 7+1 = 5+2+1 = 5+1+1+1+1 = 4+4 = 4+2+1+1 = 4+2+2 = 4+1+1+1+1 = 2+2+2+2 = 2+2+2+1+1 = 2+2+1+1+1+1 = 2+1+1+1+1+1+1 = 1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1.$$

So, there are 13 partitions i.e., $Y(8) = 13$.

$$\therefore X(n) = Y(n).$$

1.6. Generating functions for $X^1(n), Y^1(n)$ and $P_e^d(n)$:

1.6.1 The generating function for $X^1(n)$:

$X^1(n)$ is the number of partitions of n with no part repeated more than thrice given in Table-1.6

n	Partitions of n with no part repeated more than thrice	$X^1(n)$
1	1	1
2	2, 1+1	2
3	3, 2+1, 1+1+1	3
4	4, 3+1, 2+2, 2+1+1	4
5	5, 4+1, 3+2, 3+1+1, 2+2+1, 2+1+1+1	6
...	...	...

It is convenient to define $X^1(0) = 1$.

We can write an expression for $X^1(n)$ as;

$$\begin{aligned}
 & X^1(0) + X^1(1)x + X^1(2)x^2 + X^1(3)x^3 + X^1(4)x^4 + \dots \\
 &= 1 + 1.x + 2.x^2 + 3.x^3 + 4.x^4 + 6.x^5 + 9.x^6 + \dots \\
 &= (1 + x + x^2 + x^3)(1 + x^2 + x^4 + x^6)(1 + x^3 + x^6 + x^9) \dots \\
 &= \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 + x^n + x^{2n} + x^{3n}). \\
 \therefore \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 + x^n + x^{2n} + x^{3n}) &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} X^1(n)x^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

1.6.2 Generating function $Y^1(n)$ for:

$Y^1(n)$ is the number of partitions of n with no part divisible by 4 given in Table-1.7

n	Partitions of n with no part divisible by 4	$Y^1(n)$
1	1	1
2	2, 1+1	2
3	3, 2+1, 1+1+1	3
4	3+1, 2+2, 2+1+1, 1+1+1+1	4
5	5, 3+2, 3+1+1, 2+2+1, 2+1+1+1, 1+1+1+1+1	6
...	...	...

It is convenient to define $Y^1(0) = 1$.

We can write an expression for $Y^1(n)$ as;

$$\begin{aligned}
 & Y^1(0) + Y^1(1)x + Y^1(2)x^2 + Y^1(3)x^3 + Y^1(4)x^4 + Y^1(5)x^5 + \dots \\
 &= 1 + 1.x + 2.x^2 + 3.x^3 + 4.x^4 + 6.x^5 + 9.x^6 + \dots \\
 &= \frac{1}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^5)(1-x^6)(1-x^7)(1-x^9) \dots}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \prod_{n \neq 0 \pmod{4}} \frac{1}{(1-x^n)}$$

$$\therefore \prod_{n \neq 0 \pmod{4}} \frac{1}{(1-x^n)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} Y^1(n)x^n.$$

Corollary 1.3: $X^1(n) = Y^1(n)$

Proof: From above we get;

$$\sum_{n=0}^{\infty} X^1(n)x^n = \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1+x^n+x^{2n}+x^{3n})$$

$$= (1+x+x^2+x^3)(1+x^2+x^4+x^6)(1+x^3+x^6+x^9) \dots$$

$$= \frac{(1+x+x^2+x^3)(1-x)}{(1-x)} \cdot \frac{(1+x^2+x^4+x^6)(1-x^2)}{(1-x^2)} \cdot \frac{(1+x^3+x^6+x^9)(1-x^3)}{(1-x^3)} \dots$$

$$= \frac{1-x^4}{1-x} \cdot \frac{1-x^8}{1-x^2} \cdot \frac{1-x^{12}}{1-x^3} \dots$$

$$= \frac{1}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^5)(1-x^6)(1-x^7)(1-x^9) \dots}$$

$$= \prod_{n \neq 0 \pmod{4}} \frac{1}{(1-x^n)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} Y^1(n)x^n. \quad \text{[by above]}$$

$$\therefore \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} X^1(n)x^n = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} Y^1(n)x^n.$$

Equating the coefficient of x^n from both sides we get;

$$X^1(n) = Y^1(n). \text{ Hence the Corollary.}$$

Remark 1.2 [Das (2014)]: The number of partitions of n with no part repeated more than thrice is equal to the number of partitions of n with no part divisible by 4.

$$\text{i.e., } X^1(n) = Y^1(n).$$

Proof: We can prove the Remark very easily as same as the Remark 1.1 by changing four equal terms into a single term.

1.6.3. The generating function for $P_e^d(n)$:

$P_e^d(n)$ is the number of partitions of n into even distinct parts given in Table-1.8

n	Partitions of n into even distinct parts	$P_e^d(n)$
1	1	1
2	2, 1+1	2
3	3, 2+1, 1+1+1	3
4	4, 3+1, 2+1+1, 1+1+1+1	4
5	5, 4+1, 3+2, 3+1+1, 2+1+1+1, 1+1+1+1+1	6
...		...

It is convenient to define $P_e^d(0) = 1$.

We can write an expression for $P_e^d(n)$ as;

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P_e^d(0) + P_e^d(1)x + P_e^d(2)x^2 + P_e^d(3)x^3 + P_e^d(4)x^4 + \dots \\
 &= 1 + 1.x + 2.x^2 + 3.x^3 + 4.x^4 + 6x^5 + 9.x^6 + \dots \\
 &= \frac{(1+x^2)(1+x^4)(1+x^6)}{(1-x)(1-x^3)(1-x^5)} \dots \\
 &= \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1+x^{2n})}{(1-x^{2n-1})} \\
 \therefore \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1+x^{2n})}{(1-x^{2n-1})} &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_e^d(n)x^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

Corollary 2.4: $P_e^d(n) = X^1(n)$

Proof: From above we get;

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_e^d(n)x^n &= \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1+x^{2n})}{(1-x^{2n-1})} \\
 &= \frac{(1+x^2)(1+x^4)(1+x^6)}{(1-x)(1-x^3)(1-x^5)} \dots \\
 &= \frac{(1+x^2)(1+x^4)(1+x^6)}{(1-x)(1-x^3)(1-x^5)} \cdot \frac{(1-x^2)(1-x^4)(1-x^6)}{(1-x^2)(1-x^4)(1-x^6)} \\
 &= \frac{(1+x^2)(1-x^2)(1+x^4)(1-x^4)(1+x^6)(1-x^6)}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} \\
 &= \frac{(1-x^4)(1-x^8)(1-x^{12})}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} \\
 &= (1+x+x^2+x^3)(1+x^2+x^4+x^6)(1+x^3+x^6+x^9) \dots \\
 &= \prod_{n=1}^{\infty} (1+x^n+x^{2n}+x^{3n}) \\
 &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} X^1(n)x^n. \quad \text{[by above]} \\
 \therefore \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_e^d(n)x^n &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} X^1(n)x^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now equating the coefficient of x^n from both sides we get;

$$P_e^d(n) = X^1(n). \text{ Hence the Corollary.}$$

1.7. Generating functions for $C'(n)$ and $C'_1(n)$:

[Collected from Ramanujan’s lost notebook and Andrews (1979)]

1.7.1 The generating function for $C'(n)$:

$C'(n)$ is the number of partitions of n into parts of the forms $5m + 1$ and $5m + 4$ given in Table-1.9

n	Partitions of n into parts of the forms $5m + 1$ and $5m + 4$	$C'(n)$
1	1	1
2	1+1	1
3	1+1+1	1
4	4, 1+1+1+1	2
5	4+1, 1+1+1+1+1	2
6	6, 4+1+1, 1+1+1+1+1+1	3
...		...

It is convenient to define $C'(0)=1$

We can write an expression for $C'(n)$ as;

$$\begin{aligned}
 & C'(0) + C'(1)x + C'(2)x^2 + C'(3)x^3 + C'(4)x^4 + C'(5)x^5 + \dots \\
 &= 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + 2x^4 + 2x^5 + 3x^6 + \dots \\
 &= \frac{1}{(1-x)(1-x^4)(1-x^6)(1-x^9)\dots} \text{ [Hardy et al. (1917)]} \\
 &= \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{5m+1})(1-x^{5m+4})} \\
 \therefore \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{5m+1})(1-x^{5m+4})} &= 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C'(n)x^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

1.6.2 The generating function for $C'_1(n)$:

$C'_1(n)$ is the number of partitions of n into parts without repetitions or parts, whose minimal difference is 2 given in Table-1.10

n	Partitions of n into parts without repetitions or parts, whose minimal difference is 2	$C'_1(n)$
1	1	1
2	2	1
3	3	1

4	4, 3+1	2
5	5, 4+1	2
...	...	...

It is convenient to define $C'_1(0)=1$.

We can write an expression for $C'_1(n)$ as;

$$\begin{aligned}
 & C'_1(0)+C'_1(1)x+C'_1(2)x^2+C'_1(3)x^3+C'_1(4)x^4+C'_1(5)x^5+\dots \\
 & =1+x+x^2+x^3+2x^4+2x^5+3x^6+3x^7+\dots\infty \\
 & =1+\frac{x}{1-x}+\frac{x^4}{(1-x)(1-x^2)}+\frac{x^9}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)}+\dots\infty \quad [\text{Andrews (2005)}] \\
 & =1+\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{m^2}}{(1-x)(1-x^2)\dots(1-x^m)} \\
 \therefore & 1+\sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{m^2}}{(1-x)(1-x^2)\dots(1-x^m)} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} C'_1(n)x^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

1.6.3 In 1916, Ramanujan defined the following series in his Lost Notebook;

We get; $H_k(a, x) = \frac{G_k(a, x)}{(1-a)(1-ax)\dots\infty}$, [where $H_0 = 0$ and $k = 1$ or 2] ... (1.6.3a)

and $H_k = H_k(a, x) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n a^{2n} x^{\frac{n(5n+1)-2kn}{2}} (1-a^k x^{2kn}) P_n Q_n(a)$,

where $P_n = \prod_{r=1}^n \frac{1}{1-x^r}$, and $Q_n(a) = \prod_{r=n}^{\infty} \frac{1}{1-ax^r}$. It is convenient to define $P_0 = 1$.

And $G_k(a, x) = \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (-1)^n a^{2n} x^{\frac{n(5n+1)-2kn}{2}} (1-a^k x^{2kn}) C_n$ with $|x| < 1$ and $|a| < 1$.

where k is 1 or 2 and $C_0 = 1$, $C_n = \frac{(1-a)(1-ax)\dots(1-ax^{n-1})}{(1-x)(1-x^2)\dots(1-x^n)}$.

$H_k - H_{k-1} = a^{k-1} \eta H_{3-k}$, where the operator η is defined by $\eta f(a) = f(ax)$, and $k = 1$ or 2 .

..... (1.6.3b)

If $k=1$ and $a=x$ then;

$G_1(x, x) = 1 - x - x^4 + x^7 + x^{13} - \dots\infty$... (1.6.3c)

$$= \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1 - x^{5n+1})(1 - x^{5n+4})(1 - x^{5n+5})$$

Again if $k=2$ and $a=x$ then;

$$G_2(x, x) = 1 - x^2 - x^3 + x^9 + x^{11} - \dots \infty \tag{1.6.3d}$$

$$= \prod_{m=0}^{\infty} (1 - x^{5m+2})(1 - x^{5m+3})(1 - x^{5m+5}) .$$

Theorem 1.2: The number of partitions of n with minimal difference 2 is equal to the number of partitions of n into parts of the forms $5m + 1$ and $5m + 4$.

$$i.e., C'_1(n) = C'(n).$$

Proof: From Ramanujan’s Lost Notebook, we get;

$$H_k(a, x) = \frac{G_k(a, x)}{(1-a)(1-ax)\dots \infty}, [where H_0 = 0 and k = 1 or 2]$$

If $k = 2$ and $a = x$, we get;

$$H_2(x, x) = \frac{G_2(x, x)}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots \infty} = \frac{\prod_{m=0}^{\infty} (1 - x^{5m+2})(1 - x^{5m+3})(1 - x^{5m+5})}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots \infty} \tag{by(1.6.3d)}$$

$$= \frac{1}{(1-x)(1-x^4)(1-x^6)(1-x^9)(1-x^{11})(1-x^{14})\dots}$$

$$or, H_2(x, x) = \prod_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{5m+1})(1-x^{5m+4})} \dots \tag{1.6.3e}$$

Again, from Ramanujan’s Lost Notebook, we get;

$H_k - H_{k-1} = a^{k-1} \eta H_{3-k}$, where the operator η is defined by $\eta f(a) = f(ax)$, and $k = 1$ or 2 , then

$$H_1 = \eta H_2, H_2 - H_1 = a \eta H_1 .$$

So we have,

$$H_2 = \eta H_2 + a \eta^2 H_2 . \dots \tag{1.6.3f}$$

$$We\ suppose\ that;\ H_2 = 1 + c_1 a + c_2 a^2 + \dots \tag{1.6.3g}$$

where the coefficients c_i depend on x only. Substituting this into (1.6.3f), we obtain;

$$1 + c_1 a + c_2 a^2 + \dots \infty = 1 + c_1 a x + c_2 a^2 x^2 + \dots \infty + a(1 + c_1 a x^2 + c_2 a^2 x^4 + \dots \infty).$$

Hence, equating the coefficients of various powers of a from both sides we get;

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{1-x}, c_2 = \frac{x^2}{1-x^2} c_1, c_3 = \frac{x^4}{1-x^3} c_2, \dots, c_n = \frac{x^{n(n-1)}}{(1-x)(1-x^2)\dots(1-x^n)} .$$

Putting these values in(1.6.3g)

$$H_2 = H_2(a, x) = 1 + \frac{a}{1-x} + \frac{a^2 x^2}{(1-x)(1-x^2)} + \frac{a^3 x^6}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} + \dots \infty \dots \quad (1.6.3h)$$

If $a = x$, then; $H_2(x, x) = 1 + \frac{x}{1-x} + \frac{x^4}{(1-x)(1-x^2)} + \frac{x^9}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} + \dots \quad (1.6.3i)$

From (1.6.3e) and (1.6.3i) we get;

$$1 + \frac{x}{(1-x)} + \frac{x^4}{(1-x)(1-x^2)} + \frac{x^9}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} + \dots = \prod_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{5m+1})(1-x^{5m+4})}$$

$$i.e., 1 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{m^2}}{(1-x)(1-x^2)\dots(1-x^m)} = \prod_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{5m+1})(1-x^{5m+4})}$$

[It is known as Rogers- Ramanujan’s Identity]

$$\therefore 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C'_1(n)x^n = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C'(n)x^n.$$

Equating the co-efficient of x^n from both side we get;

$$C'_1(n) = C'(n)$$

i.e., the number of partitions of n with minimal difference 2 is equal to the number of partitions of n into parts of the forms $5m + 1$ and $5m + 4$. Hence the Theorem.

Example 1.3:

For $n = 11$, there are 7 partitions of 11 that are enumerated by $C'_1(n)$ of above statement, which are given bellow;

$$11, 10 + 1, 9 + 2, 8 + 3, 7 + 4, 7 + 3 + 1, 6+4+ 1, \therefore C'_1(11) = 7.$$

There are 7 partitions of 11 are enumerated by $C'(n)$ of above statement, which are given bellow:

$$11, 9+1+1, 6+4+1, 6+1+1+1+1+1, 4+4+1+1+1, 4+1+1+1+1+1+1,$$

$$1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1, \therefore C'(11) = 7.$$

Hence, $C'_1(11) = C'(11)$.

1.8. The generating functions for $C''(n)$ and $C'_1(n)$:

[Collected from Ramanujan’s lost notebook and Andrews (1988)]

1.8.1 The generating function for $C''(n)$:

$C''(n)$ is the number of partitions of n into parts of the forms $5m + 2$ and $5m + 3$ given

In Table-1.11

n	Partitions of n into parts of the forms $5m + 2$ and $5m + 3$	$C''(n)$
1	none	0
2	2	1
3	3	1

4	2+2	1
5	3+2	1
6	3+3, 2+2+2	2
...	...	...

It is convenient to define $C''(0)=1$.

We can write an expression for $C''(n)$ as;

$$\begin{aligned}
 & C''(0)+C''(1)x+C''(2)x^2+C''(3)x^3+C''(4)x^4+C''(5)x^5+\dots \\
 & =1+0.x+x^2+x^3+x^4+x^5+2x^6+2x^7+\dots\infty \\
 & =\frac{1}{(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^7)(1-x^8)\dots\infty} \quad [\text{Birman (1988)}] \\
 & =\sum_{m=0}^{\infty}\frac{1}{(1-x^{5m+2})(1-x^{5m+3})} \\
 \therefore \sum_{m=0}^{\infty}\frac{1}{(1-x^{5m+2})(1-x^{5m+3})} & =\sum_{n=0}^{\infty}C''(n)x^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

1.8.2 The generating function for $C_1''(n)$:

$C_1''(n)$ is the number of partitions of n into parts not less than 2 and with minimal difference 2 given in Table-1.12

n	Partitions of n into parts not less than 2 and with minimal difference 2	$C_1''(n)$
1	none	0
2	2	1
3	3	1
4	4	1
5	5	1
6	6, 4+2	2
...	...	...

It is convenient to define $C_1''(0)=1$.

We can write an expression for $C_1''(n)$ as;

$$\begin{aligned}
 & C_1''(0)+C_1''(1)x+C_1''(2)x^2+C_1''(3)x^3+C_1''(4)x^4+C_1''(5)x^5+\dots \\
 & =1+x^2+x^3+x^4+x^5+2x^6+2x^7+3x^8+\dots\infty
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= 1 + \frac{x^2}{1-x} + \frac{x^6}{(1-x)(1-x^2)} + \frac{x^{12}}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} + \dots \infty \\
 &= 1 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{m(m+1)}}{(1-x)(1-x^2)\dots(1-x^m)} \quad [\text{Rankin (1989) and Lovejoy (2003)}] \\
 \therefore 1 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{m(m+1)}}{(1-x)(1-x^2)\dots(1-x^m)} &= 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_1''(n)x^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 1.3: The number of partitions of n into parts not less than 2 and with minimal difference 2 is equal to the number of partitions of n into parts of the forms $5m + 2$ and $5m + 3$ i.e., $C_1''(n) = C''(n)$.

Proof: From Ramanujan’s Lost Notebook, we get;

$$H_k(a, x) = \frac{G_k(a, x)}{(1-a)(1-ax)\dots \infty}, \text{ [where } H_0 = 0 \text{ and } k = 1 \text{ or } 2]$$

If $k = 1$ and $a = x$, we get;

$$\begin{aligned}
 H_1(x, x) &= \frac{G_1(x, x)}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots \infty} = \frac{\prod_{m=0}^{\infty} (1-x^{5m+1})(1-x^{5m+4})(1-x^{5m+5})}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)\dots \infty} \text{ [by(1.6.3c)]} \\
 &= \frac{1}{(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^7)(1-x^8)(1-x^{12})(1-x^{13})\dots} \\
 &= \prod_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{5m+2})(1-x^{5m+3})}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{or, } H_1(x, x) = \prod_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{5m+2})(1-x^{5m+3})} \quad \dots \quad (1.6.3j)$$

Again, from Ramanujan’s Lost Notebook, we get

$H_k - H_{k-1} = a^{k-1} \eta H_{3-k}$, where the operator η is defined by $\eta f(a) = f(ax)$, and $k = 1$ or 2 , then

$$H_1 = \eta H_2, \quad H_2 - H_1 = a \eta H_1.$$

So we have,

$$H_2 = \eta H_2 + a \eta^2 H_2. \quad \dots \quad (1.6.3k)$$

$$\text{We suppose that; } H_2 = 1 + c_1 a + c_2 a^2 + \dots \quad (1.6.3l)$$

where the coefficients c_i depend on x only. Substituting this into (1.6.3k), we obtain;

$$1 + c_1 a + c_2 a^2 + \dots \infty = 1 + c_1 ax + c_2 a^2 x^2 + \dots \infty + a(1 + c_1 ax^2 + c_2 a^2 x^4 + \dots \infty).$$

Hence, equating the coefficients of various powers of a from both sides we get;

$$c_1 = \frac{1}{1-x}, \quad c_2 = \frac{x^2}{1-x^2} c_1, \quad c_3 = \frac{x^4}{1-x^3} c_2, \quad \dots, \quad c_n = \frac{x^{n(n-1)}}{(1-x)(1-x^2)\dots(1-x^n)}.$$

Putting these values in(1.6.3l)

$$H_2 = H_2(a, x) = 1 + \frac{a}{1-x} + \frac{a^2x^2}{(1-x)(1-x^2)} + \frac{a^3x^6}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} + \dots \infty \dots (1.6.3m)$$

From above we get; $H_1 = \eta H_2$

$$H_1 = H_1(a, x) = \eta \left\{ 1 + \frac{a}{(1-x)} + \frac{a^2x^2}{(1-x)(1-x^2)} + \frac{a^3x^6}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} + \dots \right\} \text{ [by(1.6.3m)]}$$

$$H_1 = H_1(a, x) = \left\{ 1 + \frac{ax}{(1-x)} + \frac{a^2x^4}{(1-x)(1-x^2)} + \frac{a^3x^9}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} + \dots \right\}$$

$$\text{If } a = x, \text{ then; } H_1(x, x) = \left\{ 1 + \frac{x^2}{(1-x)} + \frac{x^6}{(1-x)(1-x^2)} + \frac{x^{12}}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} + \dots \right\} (1.6.3n)$$

From (1.6.3j) and (1.6.3n) we get;

$$1 + \frac{x^2}{(1-x)} + \frac{x^6}{(1-x)(1-x^2)} + \frac{x^{12}}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} + \dots = \prod_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{5m+2})(1-x^{5m+3})}$$

$$\text{i.e., } 1 + \sum_{m=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^{m(m+1)}}{(1-x)(1-x^2) \dots (1-x^m)} = \prod_{m=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{5m+2})(1-x^{5m+3})}$$

[It is also known as Rogers- Ramanujan’s Identity]

$$\therefore 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C_1''(n)x^n = 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} C''(n)x^n.$$

Equating the co-efficient of x^n from both side we get;

$$C_1''(n) = C''(n),$$

i.e., the number of partitions of n into parts not less than 2 and with minimal difference 2 is equal to the number of partitions of n into parts of the forms $5m + 2$ and $5m + 3$. Hence the Theorem.

Example 1.4:

If $n = 11$, the four partitions of 11 into parts not less than 2 and with minimal difference 2 are given below:

11, $9 + 2$, $8 + 3$, $7 + 4$. Hence, $C_1''(11) = 4$.

Again the four partitions of 11 into parts of the form $5m + 2$ and $5m + 3$ are given as;

$8 + 3$, $7 + 2 + 2$, $3 + 3 + 3 + 2$, $3 + 2 + 2 + 2 + 2$. Hence, $C''(11) = 4$.

$$\therefore C_1''(11) = C''(11).$$

1.9. We discuss the generating functions for $P'(n)$ and $P''(n)$:

[Collected from Ramanujan’s lost notebook and Berndt (1991)]

1.9.1 The generating function for $P'(n)$:

$P'(n)$ is the number of partitions of n into parts of the form $n = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_r$, where $a_i - a_{i+1} \geq 3$

and if $3 \nmid a_i$, then $a_i - a_{i+1} > 3$ given in Table-1.13

n	Type of partitions	$P'(n)$
1	1	1

2	2	1
3	3	1
4	4	1
5	5, 4+1	2
...	...	...

It is convenient to define $P'(0) = 1$.

We can write an expression for $P'(n)$ as;

$$\begin{aligned}
 &P'(0) + P'(1)x + P'(2)x^2 + P'(3)x^3 + P'(4)x^4 + \dots \\
 &= 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + 2x^5 + 2x^6 + 3x^7 + 3x^8 + \dots \infty \\
 &= (1+x)(1+x^2)(1+x^4)(1+x^5)(1+x^7) \dots \quad [\text{Andrews (1979)}]
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1+x^{3n+1})(1+x^{3n+2}).$$

$$\therefore \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1+x^{3n+1})(1+x^{3n+2}) = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P'(n)x^n.$$

1.9.2 The generating function for $P''(n)$:

$P''(n)$ is the number of partitions of n into parts congruent to $\pm 1 \pmod{6}$

given in Table- 1.14

n	Type of partitions	$P''(n)$
1	1	1
2	1+1	1
3	1+1+1	1
4	1+1+1+1	1
5	5, 1+1+1+1+1	2
...	...	...

It is convenient to define $P''(0) = 1$.

We can write an expression for $P''(n)$ as; $P''(0) + P''(1)x + P''(2)x^2 + P''(3)x^3 + P''(4)x^4 + \dots$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= 1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + x^4 + 2x^5 + 2x^6 + 3x^7 + 3x^8 + \dots \infty \\
 &= (1+x+x^2 \dots)(1+x^5+x^{10} \dots)(1+x^7+x^{14} \dots) \dots [\text{Andrews (1979)}] \\
 &= (1-x)^{-1}(1-x^5)^{-1}(1-x^7)^{-1} \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \frac{1}{(1-x)(1-x^5)(1-x^7) \dots}$$

$$= \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{6n+1})(1-x^{6n+5})}$$

$$\therefore \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{6n+1})(1-x^{6n+5})} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P''(n)x^n.$$

Corollary 1.5: $P'(n) = P''(n)$

Proof: From above we get;

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P'(n)x^n &= \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} (1+x^{3n+1})(1+x^{3n+2}) \\ &= (1+x)(1+x^2)(1+x^4)(1+x^5)(1+x^7)(1+x^8)\dots \\ &= \frac{(1-x^2)(1-x^4)(1-x^8)\dots}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^4)\dots} \\ &= \frac{1}{(1-x)(1-x^5)(1-x^7)(1-x^{11})\dots} \\ &= \prod_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(1-x^{6n+1})(1-x^{6n+5})} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P''(n)x^n. \\ \therefore \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P'(n)x^n &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P''(n)x^n. \end{aligned}$$

Equating the coefficient of x^n from both sides we get;

$$P'(n) = P''(n). \quad \text{Hence the Corollary.}$$

Now we can consider a Partition Theorem;

Theorem 1.4: $P'(n) = P''(n)$. i.e., the number of partitions of n into parts of the form $n = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_r$, where $a_i - a_{i+1} \geq 3$ and if $3|a_i$, then $a_i - a_{i+1} > 3$ is equal to the number of partitions of n into parts congruent to $\pm 1 \pmod{6}$.

Proof: We establish an one-to-one correspondence between the partitions enumerated by $P'(n)$ and those enumerated by $P''(n)$. Firstly we consider partition enumerated by $P'(n)$, let $n = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_r$, where all terms congruent to $\pm 1 \pmod{6}$ except a_i or a_j , where $i \in [1, r]$ and $j \in [1, r]$. If a_i is multiple by 3, then a_i can be expressed the terms congruent to $1 \pmod{6}$ and a_j can be expressed the terms congruent to $\pm 1 \pmod{6}$, like;

$$9+2 = 1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1, \text{ and}$$

$$8+3 = 5+1+1+1+1+1.$$

Now we are arranging all the terms of the partition of n can be expressed the terms congruent to $\pm 1 \pmod{6}$. Consequently all the terms of the partition of n can be enumerated by $P'(n)$ can be converted to the partitions of n into parts congruent to $\pm 1 \pmod{6}$. So, our correspondence is one-to-one.

Conversely, we transfer the partitions of n enumerated by $P''(n)$. Let $n = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_r$, where all terms congruent to $\pm 1 \pmod{6}$, we sum the terms in the 1st group of n , it would be a_i (say) where $i \in [1, r]$ and sum the terms in the 2nd group of n , it would be a_{i+1} (say), $a_i - a_{i+1} \geq 3$ and if $3|a_i$, then $a_i - a_{i+1} > 3$, like: $7+1+1+1+1 = 7+4$, $5+5+1 = 10+1$ and $5+1+1+1+1+1+1 =$

8+3, then all parts of the partitions of n into parts of the form $n = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_r$, where $a_i - a_{i+1} \geq 3$ and if $3|a_i$, then $a_i - a_{i+1} > 3$. Consequently all the partitions of n enumerated by $P''(n)$ can be converted to the partitions of n enumerated by $P'(n)$. Totally our correspondence is onto i.e., the number of partitions of n into parts of the form $n = a_1 + a_2 + \dots + a_r$, where $a_i - a_{i+1} \geq 3$ and if $3|a_i$, then $a_i - a_{i+1} > 3$ is equal to the number of partitions of n into parts congruent to $\pm 1 \pmod{6}$.

i.e., $P'(n) = P''(n)$. Hence the Theorem.

Numerical example 1.5: when $n = 11$. If $n = 11$, the five partitions of 11 that are enumerated by $P'(n)$ are: 11, 10+1, 9+2, 8+3, and 7+4. The five partitions of 11 into parts congruent to $\pm 1 \pmod{6}$ are 11, 7+1+1+1+1, 5+5+1, 5+1+1+1+1+1, and 1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1+1.

i.e., $P'(11) = P''(11)$.

1.10. Consider the Generating Functions For $P_1^2(n), P_1^r(n), P_1^2(n)$ and $P_1^2(n)$, with $r \geq 2$:

[Collected from Ramanujan’s lost notebook]

1.10.1 The Generating Function for $P_1^2(n)$:

$P_1^2(n)$ is the number of partitions of n into parts that are either even and not congruent to 6 (mod8) or odd and congruent to 3,7 (mod8) given in Table-1.15

n	Partitions of n into parts that are either even and not congruent to 6 (mod8) or odd and congruent to 3,7 (mod8)	$P_1^2(n)$
1	none	0
2	2	1
3	3	1
4	4, 2+2	2
5	3+2	1
6	4+2, 3+3, 2+2+2	3
...		...

It is convenient to define $P_1^2(0) = 1$.

We can write an expression for $P_1^2(n)$ as;

$$P_1^2(0) + P_1^2(1)x + P_1^2(2)x^2 + P_1^2(3)x^3 + P_1^2(4)x^4 + P_1^2(5)x^5 + \dots$$

$$= 1 + 0.x + 1.x^2 + 1.x^3 + 2.x^4 + 1.x^5 + 3.x^6 + \dots$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{(1-x^6)(1-x^{14})\dots}{(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^4)(1-x^6)(1-x^7)(1-x^8)\dots} \quad [\text{Andrews, (1967)}] \\
 &= \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1-x^{8j-2})}{(1-x^{2j})(1-x^{4j-1})} \\
 \therefore \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1-x^{8j-2})}{(1-x^{2j})(1-x^{4j-1})} &= 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} P_1^2(n)x^n.
 \end{aligned}$$

In general, we can write

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1-x^{4rj-2})}{(1-x^{2j})(1-x^{2rj-1})} \\
 &= \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1-x^{4rj-2})(1+x^{2j}+x^{4j}+\dots\infty)(1+x^{2rj-1}+x^{4rj-2}+\dots\infty) \\
 &= 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} P_1^r(n)x^n \\
 \therefore \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1-x^{4rj-2})}{(1-x^{2j})(1-x^{2rj-1})} &= 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} P_1^r(n)x^n, \quad [\text{Ramanathan (1981)}]
 \end{aligned}$$

where the coefficient $P_1^r(n)$ is the number of partitions of n into parts that are either even and not congruent to $4r-2 \pmod{4r}$ or odd and congruent to $2r-1, 4r-1 \pmod{4r}$.

1.10.2 The Generating Function for $P_2^2(n)$:

$P_2^2(n)$ is the number of partitions of n into parts that are either even or else congruent to $3 \pmod{4}$ with the further restriction that only even parts may be repeated given in

Table-1.16

n	Partitions of n into parts that are either even or else congruent to $3 \pmod{4}$ with the further restriction that only even parts may be repeated	$P_2^2(n)$
1	none	0
2	2	1
3	3	1
4	4, 2+2	2
5	3+2	1
6	6, 4+2, 2+2+2	3
...		...

It is convenient to define $P_2^2(0)=1$.

We can write an expression for $P_2^2(n)$ as;

$$\begin{aligned} &P_2^2(0) + P_2^2(1)x + P_2^2(2)x^2 + P_2^2(3)x^3 + P_2^2(4)x^4 + P_2^2(5)x^5 + \dots \\ &= 1 + 0.x + 1.x^2 + 1.x^3 + 2.x^4 + 1.x^5 + 3.x^6 + \dots \\ &= \frac{(1+x^3)(1+x^7)(1+x^{11})\dots}{(1-x^2)(1-x^4)(1-x^6)(1-x^8)\dots} \text{ [Andrews (1967)]} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1+x^{4j-1})}{(1-x^{2j})} \\ \therefore \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1+x^{4j-1})}{(1-x^{2j})} &= 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} P_2^2(n)x^n. \end{aligned}$$

In general, we can write

$$\begin{aligned} &\prod_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1+x^{2rj-1})}{(1-x^{2j})} \\ &= \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} (1+x^{2rj-1})(1+x^{2j} + x^{4j} + \dots \infty) \\ &= 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} P_2^r(n)x^n, \\ \therefore \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1+x^{2rj-1})}{(1-x^{2j})} &= 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} P_2^r(n)x^n, \end{aligned}$$

where the coefficient $P_2^r(n)$ is the number of partitions of n into parts that are either even and not congruent to $4r-2 \pmod{4r}$ or odd and congruent to $2r-1, 4r-1 \pmod{4r}$.

Corollary 1.6: $P_1^r(n) = P_2^r(n)$

Proof: From above we get;

$$\begin{aligned} 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} P_1^r(n)x^n &= \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1-x^{4rj-2})}{(1-x^{2j})(1-x^{2rj-1})} \\ \text{or, } \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_1^r(n)x^n &= \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1-x^{2rj-1})(1+x^{2rj-1})}{(1-x^{2j})(1-x^{2rj-1})} \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{(1+x^{2rj-1})}{(1-x^{2j})} \\ &= 1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} P_2^r(n)x^n, \quad \text{[by above]} \\ &= \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} P_2^r(n)x^n, \end{aligned}$$

Equating the co-efficient of x^n from both sides we get;

$P_1^r(n) = P_2^r(n)$. Hence the Corollary.

Here we give a Theorem, which is related to the terms $P_2^r(n)$ and $P_3^r(n)$.

Theorem 1.5: The number of partitions of n into parts that are either even or odd congruent to $2r-1 \pmod{2r}$ with the further restriction that only even parts may be repeated is equal to the number of partitions of n of the form $n = b_1 + b_2 + \dots + b_s$, where $b_i \geq b_{i+1}$, and for b_i odd $b_i - b_{i+1} \geq 2r - 1$. Where $P_3^r(n)$ denote the number of partitions of n of the form $n = b_1 + b_2 + \dots + b_s$, where $b_i \geq b_{i+1}$, and for b_i odd, $b_i - b_{i+1} \geq 2r - 1$ ($1 \leq i \leq s$, where $b_{s+1} = 0$).

$$i.e., P_2^r(n) = P_3^r(n).$$

Proof: Let π_1 be a partition of the type enumerated by $P_3^r(n)$. We represent π_1 graphically with each even part $2m$ represented by two rows of m nodes and each odd part $2m + 1$ represented by two rows of $m+1$ nodes and m nodes respectively.

Such as $9 + 6$ becomes;

Now we may consider the graph vertically with the condition that r columns are always to be grouped as a single part, whenever the lowest node in the most right hand column of the group is not presented there. If $r = 2$, form above graph we obtain in this manner;

The partition $4 + 4 + 4 + 3$. Now since the condition on partitions enumerated by $P_3^r(n)$ is $b_i - b_{i+1} \geq 2r - 1$, whenever b_i is odd. Thus a part congruent to $2r - 1 \pmod{2r}$ is produced. Since originally odd parts were distinct, we see that now odd parts will be congruent to $2r - 1 \pmod{2r}$ and will not be repeated and since originally all odd parts were greater or equal to $2r - 1$, we see that there will always be r columns available for each grouping. Thus in this case we have produced a partition of the type enumerated by $P_2^r(n)$. Clearly our correspondence is one to one, however, the above process is reversible and thus the correspondence is onto. So that $P_2^r(n) = P_3^r(n)$.

Hence the Theorem.

Example 1.6: We take $r = 2, n = 9$. The corresponding partitions are listed opposite each other in the following table -1.17:

Type of partitions enumerated by $P_3^r(9)$	With relevant graph	Type of partitions enumerated by $P_2^r(9)$
9	• • • • •	$2 + 2 + 2 + 3$

Now we can write $P_3'(9) = P_2'(9) = 4$.

1.11. The Generating Functions [Andrews et al. (2013)] for FFW (n) and $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n$:

1.11.1 The generating Function for FFW (n):

FFW (n): Let D denote the set of partitions into distinct parts. We define;

$$FFW(n) = \sum_{\substack{\pi \in D \\ |\pi|=n}} (-1)^{\#(\pi)-1} s(\pi),$$

where $s(\pi)$ is the smallest part of a partition π , and $\#(\pi)$ is the number of parts given in Table-1.18

n	Partitions of n into distinct parts	$s(\pi)$	$FFW(n)$
1	1	1	1
2	2	2	2
3	3, 2+1	3, 1	2
4	4, 3+1	4, 1	3

5	5, 4+1,3+2	5, 1, 2	2
6	6, 5+1, 4+2, 3+2+1	6, 1, 2, 1	4
...	...		

We can write an expression for $FFW(n)$ as;

$$\begin{aligned}
 & FFW(1)x + FFW(2)x^2 + FFW(3)x^3 + FFW(4)x^4 + \dots \\
 &= x + 2x^2 + 2x^3 + 3x^4 + 2x^5 + 4x^6 + \dots \\
 &= \frac{x}{(1-x)(1-x)} + \frac{(-1)x^3}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^2)} + \frac{x^6}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)(1-x^3)} + \dots \\
 & \qquad \qquad \qquad \text{[Fokkink et al. (1995)]} \\
 &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n+1}{2}}}{(x)_n (1-x^n)} \\
 &\therefore \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n+1}{2}}}{(x)_n (1-x^n)} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(n).
 \end{aligned}$$

Relation 2.1. $FFW(n) = d(n)$

Proof: A relation related to the term $d(n)$.

- We get; $FFW(1) = 1 = d(1)$
 $FFW(2) = 2 = d(2)$
 $FFW(3) = 2 = d(3)$
 $FFW(4) = 3 = d(4)$
 $FFW(5) = 2 = d(5)$
 --- --- ---

We can write the relation $FFW(n) = d(n)$. Hence the Relation.

Corollary 2.7: $\frac{x}{(1-zx)(1-x)} = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{z^k - 1}{z - 1} \right) x^k$

Proof: L.H.S = $\frac{x}{(1-zx)(1-x)}$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= x(1 + zx + z^2x^2 + z^3x^3 + \dots)(1 + x + x^2 + x^3 + \dots) \\
 &= x + (1+z)x^2 + (1+z+z^2)x^3 + (1+z+z^2+z^3)x^4 + \dots \\
 &= x + \frac{(1+z)(1-z)}{(1-z)}x^2 + \frac{(1+z+z^2)(1-z)}{(1-z)}x^3 + \frac{(1+z+z^2+z^3)(1-z)}{(1-z)}x^4 + \dots \\
 &= x + \frac{(1-z^2)}{(1-z)}x^2 + \frac{(1-z^3)}{(1-z)}x^3 + \frac{(1-z^4)}{(1-z)}x^4 + \dots \\
 &= x + \frac{(z^2-1)}{(z-1)}x^2 + \frac{(z^3-1)}{(z-1)}x^3 + \frac{(z^4-1)}{(z-1)}x^4 + \dots
 \end{aligned}$$

$$= \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \left(\frac{z^k - 1}{z - 1} \right) x^k = \text{R.H.S.} \quad \text{Hence the Corollary.}$$

Corollary 2.8:
$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(1 - zx^n)(x)_n}$$

Proof: We get;

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (x^n + (1+z)x^{2n} + \dots + (1+z+\dots+z^{k-1})x^{kn} + \dots) \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{(x)_{n-1}} \\ &\quad [\text{Andrews et al (2013) and Andrews, Encycl. Math. (1985)}] \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left\{ x^n + \frac{(1+z)(1-z)}{(1-z)} x^{2n} + \frac{(1+z+z^2)(1-z)}{(1-z)} x^{3n} + \dots \right\} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{(x)_{n-1}} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left\{ x^n + \frac{z^2-1}{z-1} x^{2n} + \frac{z^3-1}{z-1} x^{3n} + \dots \right\} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{(x)_{n-1}} \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{z^k - 1}{z - 1} x^{nk} \right) \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{(x)_{n-1}} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{x^n}{(1 - zx^n)(1 - x^n)} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n-1)}{2}}}{(x)_{n-1}} \quad [\text{by above}] \\ &= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(1 - zx^n)(x)_n} \end{aligned}$$

[Since $\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - x^n)(x)_{n-1} = (1 - x) + (1 - x^2)(1 - x) + (1 - x^3)(1 - x^2)(1 - x) + \dots = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (x)_n$]

$$\therefore \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(1 - zx^n)(x)_n} . \text{ Hence the Corollary.}$$

Corollary 2.9:
$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{(x)_k} [(x)_k - (x)_{\infty}]$$

Proof: We get;

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n &= x + (1+z)x^2 + (z+z^2)x^3 + (z+z^2+z^3)x^4 + (-1+z^2+z^3+z^4)x^5 + \dots \\ &= x + x^2 + z(x^2 + x^3 + x^4) + z^2(x^3 + x^4) + z^3x^4 + \dots \\ &= \{1 - (x)_{\infty}\} + \frac{z}{(1-x)} \{(1-x) - (x)_{\infty}\} + \frac{z^2}{(1-x)(1-x^2)} \{(1-x)(1-x^2) - (x)_{\infty}\} \\ &\quad + \frac{z^3}{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3)} \{(1-x)(1-x^2)(1-x^3) - (x)_{\infty}\} + \dots \\ &= \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{(x)_k} [(x)_k - (x)_{\infty}]. \end{aligned}$$

$$\therefore \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n = \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{(x)_k} [(x)_k - (x)_{\infty}]. \text{ Hence the Corollary.}$$

Corollary 2.10: $FFW(1, n) = FFW(n)$

Proof: We get;
$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(x)_n (1-zx^n)}$$

$$= x + (1+z)x^2 + (z+z^2)x^3 + (z+z^2+z^3)x^4 + (-1+z^2+z^3+z^4)x^5 + (-1+1+z^2+z^3+z^4+z^5)x^6 + \dots$$

Or,
$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(z, n)x^n = x + (1+z)x^2 + (z+z^2)x^3 + (z+z^2+z^3)x^4 + (-1+z^2+z^3+z^4)x^5 + \dots$$

If $z=1$, we get;

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(1, n)x^n = x + 2x^2 + 2x^3 + 3x^4 + 2x^5 + 4x^6 + \dots$$

$$= \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(x)_n (1-x^n)} \quad [\text{by above}]$$

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(1, n)x^n = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} FFW(n)x^n .$$

Equating the co-efficient of x^n form both sides we get;

$\therefore FFW(1, n) = FFW(n)$. Hence the Corollary.

2. CONCLUSION

In this article we have shown $C_1'(n) = C'(n)$ with the help of a numerical example when $n = 11$, and have shown $C_1''(n) = C''(n)$ with the help of a numerical example when $n = 11$. We have proved the Theorem $P_1^r(n) = P_3^r(n)$ for any positive integer of n and $r \geq 2$. In this article we have found the number of partitions of n into distinct parts with required conditions. We have proved the Corollaries containing a pair of generating functions

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(-1)^{n-1} x^{\frac{n(n+1)}{2}}}{(x)_n (1-zx^n)}, \frac{1}{(1-z)} \left\{ 1 - \frac{(x)_{\infty}}{(zx)_{\infty}} \right\} \text{ and } \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} \frac{z^k}{(x)_k} [(x)_k - (x)_{\infty}], \sum_{k=0}^{\infty} z^k \left\{ 1 - (x^{k+1}; x)_{\infty} \right\}$$

by simplifications. We have established the Corollary $FFW(1, n) = FFW(n)$ by taking $z=1$.

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